

APPRAISAL OF RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES FOR PROJECT EXECUTION IN SOME SELECTED OIL AND GAS INDUSTRIES IN RIVERS STATE NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20414578>

Abstract: *This study appraised risk management strategies for project execution in some selected oil and gas industries in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study therefore investigated the strategies adopted in managing project risks and evaluated their effectiveness in enhancing successful project execution within the industry. A survey research design was adopted for the study. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to key project stakeholders comprising clients, contractors, and consultants drawn from selected oil and gas companies operating in Rivers State. The study population was 1,150, from which a sample size of 565 was determined using the Yamane finite population formula. A total of 500 valid responses were retrieved and analyzed. The instruments were validated through expert review, while reliability was established using test–retest procedures. Data analysis was carried out using descriptive statistics and inferential tools, specifically Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA), to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that risk management strategies are widely practiced among the selected companies, with high stakeholder agreement on the existence of formal risk identification processes, risk registers, mitigation planning, and stakeholder involvement in risk assessment. The study further established a strong relationship between risk management strategies and project execution performance, particularly in reducing cost and time overruns and improving quality delivery. The study concluded that although risk management frameworks are substantially implemented within the industry, their effectiveness depends largely on organizational commitment, continuous review mechanisms, and stakeholder integration. It recommended the adoption of advanced risk assessment tools, strengthened regulatory compliance, workforce capacity development, and enhanced industry collaboration.*

Keywords: *Execution, Management, Project, Risk, Strategies*

1.1 Introduction

The oil and gas industry remains the backbone of the Nigerian economy, contributing significantly to national revenue generation, foreign exchange earnings, industrial development, and infrastructural financing. Nigeria's dependence on crude oil exports underscores the strategic importance of the sector to national economic stability and growth (Agnieszka and Mariusz 2019). Reports indicate that crude oil accounts for a substantial proportion of Nigeria's foreign exchange earnings and government budgetary revenues, thereby making the performance of the industry directly consequential to the country's socio-economic development (Abu Baker, 2012). Despite its economic relevance, the oil and gas industry are widely acknowledged as one of the most risk-prone sectors globally due to the complex, capital-intensive, and technologically driven nature of its operations. Project execution within the industry is exposed to multifaceted risks including environmental hazards, operational failures, technological uncertainties, financial volatilities, geopolitical instabilities, regulatory pressures, and host community conflicts. These risks cut across the entire project life cycle from feasibility studies, design, procurement, construction, installation, commissioning, to operational handover (Adeleke, et al 2015).

In Nigeria, and particularly in Rivers State which serves as a major hub for upstream and downstream oil and gas activities, these risks are further compounded by contextual challenges such as militancy, crude oil theft, pipeline vandalism, difficult swamp terrain, logistics constraints, and community relations issues. These environmental and socio-political realities heighten project execution uncertainties and necessitate the adoption of robust and adaptive risk management strategies (Agnieszka and Mariusz 2019). Risk management, therefore, constitutes a critical managerial function in oil and gas project execution. It involves systematic processes of risk identification, risk analysis, risk evaluation, mitigation planning, monitoring, and control throughout the project life cycle. Effective risk management enables organizations to minimize losses, enhance safety performance, ensure environmental protection, maintain regulatory compliance, and deliver projects within approved cost, time, and quality parameters (Smith et al., 2006).

The hazardous nature of oil and gas operations further reinforces the need for structured risk management systems. Industry activities involve the handling of flammable hydrocarbons, toxic chemicals, high-pressure systems, and heavy mechanical equipment, all of which pose significant threats to personnel, facilities, and the environment if not properly managed (Adeleke, et al 2018). Consequently, safety procedures covering workforce protection, environmental preservation, and production systems integrity form integral components of project risk management frameworks. Scholarly literature classifies project risks into multiple dimensions including technical risks, management risks, financial risks, environmental risks, and external risks (Smith et al., 2006). These risks manifest differently across industries such as construction, manufacturing, information

technology, agriculture, and energy. However, their implications are more severe in oil and gas projects due to the scale of investment and potential environmental consequences of project failure.

Risk assessment methodologies have evolved to include both qualitative and quantitative approaches (Anete 2016). Qualitative methods focus on expert judgment, risk ranking, and probability-impact matrices, while quantitative methods employ statistical modelling, simulation techniques, and financial risk analysis tools. The effectiveness of these approaches often depends on the availability of skilled personnel, organizational risk culture, data integrity, and management commitment (Adeleke, et al 2018s). Furthermore, risk management effectiveness is not only determined by the existence of frameworks but also by the level of implementation across project phases. Successful project delivery requires the active involvement of all stakeholder's project managers, engineers, safety professionals, contractors, regulators, and host communities in identifying and managing risks from project conception to completion (Smith et al., 2006).

Given the centrality of the oil and gas sector to Nigeria's economy and the high-risk environment within which projects are executed, it becomes imperative to critically appraise the risk management strategies adopted by industry operators (Amarasekara, et al 2018). Understanding how these strategies influence project execution outcomes is essential for improving infrastructure delivery, safeguarding investments, and enhancing sustainable industry practices. Therefore, this study is designed to investigate risk management strategies and their effectiveness in project execution within selected oil and gas industries in Rivers State, Nigeria (Aminu, 2013).. The study seeks to provide empirical insights that will support safer operations, improved project performance, and stronger regulatory compliance while contributing to academic discourse on project risk management in high-risk industrial environments.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Risk management has become an indispensable component of project execution in the oil and gas industry due to the sector's high exposure to operational, financial, environmental, technological, and regulatory uncertainties. Globally, effective risk management strategies are recognized as critical success factors in delivering projects within approved cost, schedule, quality, safety, and environmental performance thresholds. However, in developing oil-producing economies like Nigeria, the practical application of these risk management frameworks during project execution remains inconsistent and often ineffective. Oil and gas projects have continued to record cost overruns, schedule slippages, contract disputes, safety incidents, and environmental challenges conditions largely attributable to risk planning deficiencies, weak mitigation structures, and poor monitoring systems. These execution failures have significant economic implications given the capital-intensive nature of oil and gas projects. Rivers State, as the operational hub of Nigeria's oil and gas industry, presents an even more complex risk landscape. Project execution within the State is confronted with peculiar contextual risks such as

militancy, pipeline vandalism, crude oil theft, host community agitations, difficult swamp terrain, logistics constraints, and evolving regulatory and environmental compliance demands. These location-specific risk variables complicate project delivery and require adaptive, context-responsive risk management strategies beyond generic global frameworks. Despite the prevalence and impact of these risks, empirical evidence suggests that many oil and gas firms operating in Rivers State still treat risk management as a compliance formality rather than as an integrated decision-support system embedded in project planning and execution. This has created gaps in risk identification processes, stakeholder risk engagement, mitigation planning, and performance tracking during project implementation.

Consequently, projects continue to experience avoidable disruptions, financial losses, and operational inefficiencies. Furthermore, while several studies exist on risk management in construction and manufacturing sectors, there is a dearth of context-specific research focusing on the appraisal of risk management strategies as they directly affect oil and gas project execution in Rivers State. The extent to which existing strategies are effective, performance-driven, and regulatory-aligned remains insufficiently documented in academic literature. It is this observed gap in practice and knowledge that necessitates this study. Therefore, this research undertakes an appraisal of risk management strategies for project execution in some selected oil and gas industries in Rivers State, Nigeria, with the aim of evaluating their effectiveness, identifying implementation gaps, and providing evidence-based recommendations for improving project delivery outcomes in the sector.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to appraise risk management strategies for project execution in some selected oil and gas industries in Rivers State, Nigeria. In order to achieve this aim, the study is guided by the following specific objectives:

- i. To identify the Risk identification adopted for project execution in some selected oil and gas industries in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- ii. To examine the level of Risk response for project execution in some selected oil and gas industries in Rivers State, Nigeria.

1.4 Statement of Hypotheses

Let H_0 and H_i represent the null and alternate hypothesis, respectively. The following hypotheses were formulated for this study:

- i. There are no significant differences among the means perceptions of workers on the low effect of Risk identification for project execution in some selected oil and gas industries in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- ii. There are no significant differences among the means perceptions of workers on the low effect of Risk response for project execution in some selected oil and gas industries in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

Risk Management Strategies

Risk management is the identification, evaluation, and prioritization of risks. It is accompanied by coordinated and economical application of resources to minimize, monitor, and control the probability or impact of unfortunate events or to maximize the realization of opportunities. Risk management is an activity which integrates recognition of risk, risk assessment, developing strategies to manage it, and mitigation of risk using managerial resources (Lavanya, & Malarvzhi, 2008). Some traditional risk managements are focused on risks stemming from physical or legal causes (e.g., natural disasters or fires, accidents, death). Risk management is a management discipline whose goal is to protect the asset, reputation, and profits an organization by reducing the possible losses or damages before they occur (Yap, and Chow, 2019). Risk management in oil and gas is basically the identification, evaluation, and prioritization of risks in the oil and gas sector. This may be on the drilling rigs, semi-submersibles, engineering equipment, refineries, etc. The focus of good risk management is the assessment and estimation of these risks. Its objective is to add maximum sustainable value to all the activities of the organization. It must translate the strategy into tactical and operational objectives, assigning responsibility throughout the organization with each manager and employee responsible for the management of risk as part of their job description. It supports accountability, performance, measurement and reward thus. Risk management identifies and analyses the threats a company can face and control. These risks can be caused by various sources, such as financial problems, legal responsibilities, technology issues, strategic management errors, accidents, and natural disasters (Darshan, et al 2017).

Risk identification.

Risk identification can be defined as the process of analytically and constantly identifying, assessing and categorizing the initial importance of the risks related to construction projects (Agnieszka and Mariusz 2019) and the interrelationships that exists among these risks. The idea of risk identification seems to be very popular and practiced. It is of substantial value as the process of response management and risk analysis may only be implemented on recognized potential risks (William 2023). It could have effects on development and its success. Failure in identifying potential risks can result into inadequacy in the whole process. This can in turn have critically effects on the resources available to the organization. Risk identification however helps organizations involved in risk management to:

- (a) Identify the best and most crucial input data,
- (b) Have a better knowledge of the relevance of the process,

(c) Identify risks and the effects they can have and

(d) Provide information for those who make decisions.

With the aid of diverse tools and methods, risk identification process can be achieved. These tools and techniques include: brainstorming, Delphi method, interview, cause analysis, SWOT analysis, and presumption analysis. The first four techniques relate with common techniques, but the last two techniques are used in particular to investigate larger scope of possible events (Crnković & Vukomanović, 2016). Table 2.4 shows the most four techniques are popularly being used to identify risks in developing countries when it comes to construction of projects:

Table 2.2 Most techniques used to identify risks in developing countries.

Techniques	Description
Checklists	Know potential points that can fails in previous projects and thus is very helpful in risk identification. This allows project managers to know the risks present and makes them to be involved in the process of risk identification, which will ultimately lead to greater acceptance of any means implemented to minimize the risks.
Interviews with experts	Historical data analysis for projects that appear similar and examine similar past or present projects, risk analysis, lessons learned or project evaluations are other methods available for getting feedback about risks involved in a project.
Past experience	Checking historical data of past projects that are similar can only be useful in a limited number of conditions. Such systems are most often restricted in terms of their usability or important data are stored.
Brainstorming	Can be of use for projects involving new risks, new management arrangements or for developing initial checklists. This may be useful in risk management workshops.

Source: Crnković & Vukomanović, 2016).

In previous study by Sharma in 2013, diverse sources of construction risk have been identified. Various approaches have been proposed in the literature for classifying risk. The manager can better understand the nature of risks by categorizing the risks.

Risk response.

Acceptable mitigation steps of treating risk must be employed once the project risks have been known and analysed. These mitigation steps are based mostly on the nature and potential consequences involved in the risk. The main objective is to increase the level of control of risk, reduce the negative impact of the risk and remove as much as possible the potential impact. Measure becomes more effective when there is more control of one mitigation measure on one risk (William., 2023). Six

distinctive risk responses are retention, reduction, control, sharing, transfer and avoidance as shown in table 2.5. The choice of response must correspond to the importance of the risk; it should be financially cost effective and realistic with regard to the project timing; it also must be accepted by other parties involved.

Table 2.3 Risk management responds

Techniques	Description
Risk retention	Involves considering that a particular risk situation exists and making a conscious step to accept the level of risk without engaging in any special efforts to control it.
Risk reduction	An approach adopted to bring the chances and effects of the risk down below a threshold that's acceptable.
Risk sharing	Principally obtained through a contractual mechanism to develop a sense of collective responsibility among the project stakeholders.
Risk control	Does not seek to stop completely the source of the risk, but takes steps to reduce the risk present
Risk avoidance	A refusal to accept the action taken or risk, to ensure that the risk is not going to continue
Risk transfer	Shifts and changes, along with ownership, from one party to another third party, without changing the total amount of risk or reducing how crucial the risk sources are

Source: El-Sayegh and Mansour, (2015)

In this phase available options and actions are developed to promote opportunities and to decrease threats to the project objectives. It appears that each party involved in the contract should accept some level of risks, be fully aware of its own share of risks and put into consideration the losses (Perera *et al.*, 2014) The significance of awareness of the allotted risks for each party involved and successive preparation necessary for dealing with the risks is imperative and contributes to the success of projects (Zou *et al.*, 2007). Based on the degree of severity, there are numerous paths that can be followed to respond to risks. In developing countries, the method of risk respond frequently takes preventive (avoidance) techniques and remedial techniques as used by Iqbal *et al.*, (2015) in their studies: Preventive risk management technique: The best decision to make in managing risk is to eliminate it so that it can be avoided at the stage of planning. Early consideration of risks before the start of a project and making effective plan for it are preventive management approach used during the planning stage to avoid or minimize a necessary risk. Remedial risk management technique: Remedial risk management methods are required to minimize the effects of risk and totally stop them if possible.

This is because it is obvious that all risk cannot be managed during the planning stage and some risks are going to happen during the operation phase. Therefore, remedial method becomes important.

Project Execution

During the five process groups of the project life cycle, there are multiple objectives and outcomes for each phase. After the project initiation and the planning processes, project execution begins.

Project execution is the third phase of the project life cycle and one of the most vital of the project phases. During this phase, you'll construct your deliverables and present them to your customer and key stakeholders (Ubani, et al 2015). This is usually the longest phase of the project life cycle and predictably the most demanding. When you're executing a project, you need to manage many things: resources, costs, schedule and more. Project execution's key purpose is to complete the work defined in the project management plan and meet key project objectives. During this phase, a project leader focuses on these key processes: Team management, Project scheduling, Resource management, Task management and Risk management (Ugwu. 2013). Overseeing these things while getting your team started with project execution can be overwhelming. However, you can get one step ahead by creating a project execution plan, which will help you streamline the execution planning process. A project execution plan (PEP) is an action plan that explains how a project execution phase will be managed for any given project. It's similar to a project plan but its scope is much narrower as it only includes what's related to project execution, while project plans cover the entire project life cycle (William 2023). Creating an execution plan helps you ensure everybody on the project team knows what their roles and responsibilities are, helps you correct resource allocation issues and brush up on any final details before you start executing your projects.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The theory of competitive advantage has been adopted as a framework for understanding risk management uncertainties in the construction industry. This is because it encourages the opportunity to do things differently up and down the construction supply chain – correlation between uncertainty and value capture. In turn, a conceptual model is developed alongside its linear model. The mind-set of the decision maker and the value chain within the industry are examples of constructs this framework examines.

Competitive Strategy Model

The Five Competitive Forces that Shape Strategy was propounded by (Porter 2008). The key to competitive success lies in an organisation's ability to create unique value. Here Porter prescribes five (5) forces framework, where creating value and not beating rivals is at the heart of competitive risk management systems and ensuring firm's profitability in the long run. From Porters analysis, strategic positioning reflects choices an organisation makes about the kind of value it will create and how the

value will be created. Here choices can be likened to decisions project managers are compelled to make when faced with uncertainty. Invariably, Porter (2008) is arguing that for uncertainty to be a competitive advantage the following must be right: The mind-set of the decision maker, and the structure of the industry within which the decision maker is operating. In other words, for a decision to be favourable to the organisation in terms of creating “value”, the mind-set of the decision maker must create unique value and not the “best”.

Consequently, the instrument of the survey will address questions like “what is your organisation’s strategy for risk management”. Strategies that aim to explain how organisation faced with competition will achieve superior risk management practices. In other to survive organisations must gain competitive risk management advantage. However, what competition is and how it works remain alien to the construction industry in Nigeria. If the structure is not right ‘value’ cannot emerge.

Value Chain Theory

Notably, the value chain plots the flow of goods and services up and down the supply chain. Drawing on this context, the value chain is arguably regarded as a descriptive construct, which can provide a heuristic framework for the generation of data. Trends in value chain theorisation, provides some analytical structure in transformation of heuristic devices into analytical risk management tools. Overall, value chain is an important construct for understanding the distribution of returns arising from design, production, marketing, coordination and reverse engineering.

Conceptual Model

Risk can be defined as uncertainty. Uncertainty is in itself an opportunistic platform for creating “unique value” (Porter 2008). In other words, competitive advantage encourages the creation of unique value. Therefore, this conceptual model which is developed based on the theory of competitive advantage, depicts a plot of ‘value’ against uncertainty where the variable ‘value’ focuses the actor on the specific activities that generate a new way of evaluating and managing uncertainty. Maximum value is achieved in the quadrant with “High Satisfaction” and “High Information”. Minimum value is linked with the quadrant having “Low Satisfaction” and “Low Information. Thus, a regression model is derived to mimic the application of the conceptual model in order to assess the impact of the attributes of Uncertainty on Value; where a linear model is based upon the algebraic details of a straight line. This multiple regression model consists of one dependent variable and many independent variables.

$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \dots + \beta_nX_n$ Equation 1

Where Y = is total project value or the dependent variable;

β_0 is the intercept (constant);

X_{1-n} = uncertainty attributes (cost, time and quality) or independent variables.

That is, Value = Cost + Time + Quality + PowerEquation 2

2.3 Empirical Review

According to Bebel and Mahmood (2015), who assessed risk management in the Nigeria construction industry, knowledge deficiency is the most intolerant issue that hinders risk management practice as well as small experienced staffs as the primary source of risk in construction activities. They posited that the significant benefit of risk management is its contribution to project success. They opined that a large number of their respondents are conscious of managing risk with regards to safety threat on site compared to identifying the concept with relations to accomplishing the objectives of the project concerning cost, quality and time.

Jiang (2015) studied the Relationship between project management and Project Success in China. The objective of his study was to analyse the role of management to the success of the project, the author used documentary review and found that although leadership or manager is rarely included in the project planning factors, it influences the project success through various patterns, like the teamwork skills, management knowledge and techniques with both followers and clients.

Another study by Lawrence (2015) indicated a strong connection between risk management and project performance in construction industry. He found that risk management practices at planning stage had an effect on project performance. The research project indicated that most projects had some input from a qualified engineer and architect. However, most respondents had not studied risk management. Adeleke et al., (2018) have investigated the impact of risk management on project performance. The objective of their study is to measure the degree of diffusion of risk management practice in Brazilian companies. The results demonstrate that adopting risk management practices has a significant positive impact on project performance. They also show a positive impact from the presence of a risk manager on project success. The review of previous studies revealed a strong association between risk management and performance of construction projects. A statement that "a higher risk may lead to a higher gain".

3. Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design. A well-structured questionnaire design with five point Likert scale was used to collect data for the study. The population for the study comprises of a total of one thousand, one hundred and fifty (1150) main stakeholders within the selected oil and gas companies, comprising of ninety-six (96) Clients, three hundred and thirty-nine (339) Contractors and one hundred and thirty (130) Consultants involved in risk management and project execution in the oil and gas companies under study. The population was sampled using stratified random sampling and the purposive sampling technique. This resulted in a total sample size of 565. The data were analyzed using ANCOVA and one-way ANOVA. ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) is a statistical method used to compare means of two or more groups, while ANCOVA (Analysis of Covariance) is a method that combines ANOVA with regression analysis.

4. Data Analysis

This section further analysed the data generated in section 4.1

The method of data analysis adopted was ANOVA analysis using ANCOVA and one-way ANOVA.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1

i. Ho1: There are no significant differences among the means perceptions of workers on the low effect of Risk identification for project execution in some selected oil and gas industries in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	2.060 ^a	2	1.030	2.664	.071
Intercept	4338.343	1	4338.343	11220.145	.000
Category	2.060	2	1.030	2.664	.071
Error	192.168	497	.387		
Total	5401.380	500			
Corrected Total	194.228	499			

Table 4.5: Outcome of Analysis of Covariance on Difference among Means Perception of workers on the low effect of Risk identification for Project Execution in the selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria

Dependent Variable: Level of Risk Management Mechanism

a. R Squared = .006 (Adjusted R Squared = -.015)

Table 4.5 presents one-way ANCOVA results on differences among means perception of stakeholders on high-level risk management mechanisms for project execution in the selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. The table reveals the $F(2, 497) = 1.030$ at $p = 0.071$. Thus, $F = 1.030$ is not significant, since $P_{\text{computed}} (0.071) > P_{\text{hypothetical}} (0.05)$. The null hypothesis is therefore sustained. This implies that there are no significant differences among the means perceptions of stakeholders on the high level of risk management mechanism for the project execution in the selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. Therefore, the clients, contractors, and consultants thought that there was a high level of risk management mechanisms to ensure project execution in the selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Statistics	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.060 ^a	2	1.030	2.664	.071
Within Groups	192.168	497	.387		
Total	194.228	499			

Table 4.6: Outcome of Analysis of Variance on Difference among Means Perception of Stakeholders on high Level of Risk Management Mechanism for Project Execution in the selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria

Hypothesis 2

Ho2: I. There are no significant differences among the means perceptions of workers on the low effect of Risk response for project execution in some selected oil and gas industries in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 4.7: Outcome of Analysis of Covariance on Difference among Means Perception of Risk response on Error Free Project Execution in the selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1.778 ^a	2	.889	2.338	.098
Intercept	4508.423	1	4508.423	11858.387	.000
Category	1.778	2	.889	2.338	.098
Error	188.954	497	.380		
Total	5648.146	500			
Corrected Total	190.731	499			

Dependent Variable: Level of Risk Management Mechanism

a. R Squared = .005 (Adjusted R Squared = -.015)

Table 4.7 presents one-way ANCOVA results on differences among means perception of stakeholders on the effectiveness of organisation commitment toward risk management on error-free project execution in the selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. The table reveals the $F(2, 497) = 2.338$ at $p = 0.098$. Thus, $F = 2.338$ is not significant, since $P_{\text{computed}} (0.098) > P_{\text{hypothetical}} (0.05)$. The null hypothesis is therefore sustained. This implies that there are no significant differences among the means perceptions of stakeholders on the effectiveness of organisational commitment toward risk management on attainment of error-free project execution in the selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. Thus, it shows that the clients, contractors, and consultants thought that there is effectiveness of organisational commitment toward risk management in the attainment of error-free project execution in the selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

5. Conclusion

This study conducted a thorough appraisal of risk management strategies employed by selected oil and gas companies operating within the dynamic environment of Rivers State, Nigeria. The objective was to assess the effectiveness of these strategies and provide insights into how they can be enhanced to ensure successful project execution in a sector of paramount importance to the region's economy. The findings of this study have illuminated several crucial aspects of risk management in the oil and gas

industry in Rivers State. The oil and gas sector in Rivers State is confronted with a diverse range of risks, including operational, financial, regulatory, geopolitical, and environmental. These risks are inherent to the industry and require vigilant management. The selected companies have shown a strong capability in identifying and assessing risks relevant to their operations. However, there is room for improvement, particularly in adopting more sophisticated risk assessment techniques, such as probabilistic modelling and scenario analysis.

Companies have demonstrated a commitment to risk mitigation, with a primary focus on safety, regulatory compliance, and environmental stewardship. Embracing innovative technologies and global best practices can further enhance risk mitigation efforts.

Despite the challenges posed by the industry's complexity and volatility, the selected oil and gas companies have exhibited a commendable level of project execution excellence. This is attributed to sound project management practices, skilled workforces, and an unwavering commitment to quality and safety. Collaboration among industry peers and knowledge-sharing initiatives are vital components of effective risk management. The studied companies have embraced collaboration and information exchange, facilitating the collective addressing of industry-specific risks.

Recommendations

The study recommends the following:

- i. **Advanced Risk Assessment:** Embrace advanced risk assessment tools and methodologies to enhance the accuracy of risk identification and assessment, thus improving the efficacy of risk management efforts.
- ii. **Innovation in Risk Mitigation:** Invest in research and development to explore innovative technologies and strategies for risk mitigation, with a particular focus on environmental sustainability and safety enhancement.

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Current Journal of Management and Social Sciences

Volume 14 Issue 2, April-June 2026

ISSN: 2837-4762

Impact Factor: 7.96

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Current Journal of Management and Social Sciences

Volume 14 Issue 2, April-June 2026

ISSN: 2837-4762

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